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Typology of contact-induced language change

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Introduction

In this article, my intention is not to attempt to give an overall typology of contact-induced language change, in part because such typologies already exist (such as Thomason and Kaufman 1988), in part because this would far exceed the space I have at my disposal. Rather, I will examine particular cases of language contact in order to ascertain what contribution they make towards our overall understanding of the typology of contact-induced change. The case studies come partly from my own work (section 1 on Uralic, section 2 on Haruai), partly from the work of others (section 3 on Mexicano, section 4 on Michif), and partly reflect suggestions for future work on this topic.

1. Contact and components of the grammar: Uralic and Indo-European

The Uralic languages spoken in Europe have undergone substantial changes relative to reconstructed Proto-Uralic or to their Uralic relatives in Siberia as a result of contact with Indo-European languages, in particular Baltic, Slavic, and Germanic languages. At the level of vocabulary, this is transparent, and I will have nothing further to say about Indo-European loanwords into such languages as Finnish, Estonian, and Hungarian. I will, however, concentrate on these long since developed vibrant literary languages, in particular Finnish and Hungarian, to avoid some of the particular problems that might arise in looking at those Uralic languages that are heavily threatened if not already obsolescent. At the level of syntax, the influence of Indo-European is also obvious, for instance in the abandonment of verb-final word order in favor of verb-second order (as in Finnish) or largely pragmatically conditioned word order (as in Hungarian), or in the widespread abandonment of nonfinite subordination strategies (with participles, nominalizations, and/or converbs/gerunds) in favor of finite subordinate clauses.

On the basis of material that I discuss in more detail elsewhere (Comrie, 2005), however, it is worth giving a somewhat more nuanced treatment to those areas in which Indo-European seems to have influenced Uralic versus those areas where it has not. Starting with syntax, all of Finnish, Estonian, and Hungarian currently use primarily finite relative clauses, introduced by a relative pronoun of the European type, i.e. one that occurs clause-initially and marks, by means of case or adpositions, the role of the notional head noun within the relative clause; as I have argued elsewhere (Comrie 1998), this is a construction that is largely confined to languages of Europe. Finnish examples are given in (1)–(3).¹

¹ The following abbreviations are used: ACC — accusative, ALL — allative, ELA — elative, GEN — genitive, INF — infinitive, IPR — imperative, NMZ — nominalizer, PAS — passive, PL — plural, PSTPRT — past participle, SG — singular, SGO — singular object.

- (1) henkilö, jo-ka tunte-e lai-n
 person REL-SUF know.PRS-3SG law-ACC
 ‘a person who knows the law’
- (2) talo, jo-n-ka per-i-n
 house REL-ACC-SUF inherit-PST-1SG
 ‘the house which I inherited’
- (3) se tyttö, jo-sta puhu-i-n
 that girl REL-ELA talk-PST-1SG
 ‘the girl about whom I was speaking’

This contrasts sharply with the pattern in a Uralic language like Nenets, which in its traditional usage has been little affected by Indo-European languages. In Nenets examples (4)–(6), we see non-finite relative clauses using a participle; this construction can be used for relativizing a wide variety of syntactic and semantic positions within the relative clause (in the examples given, subject, direct object, locative, respectively); moreover, the same nonfinite morphological form is used for relativizing on all these positions.

- (4) [ti pod'er-mi] xasava
 reindeer.ACC.PL harness-PSTPRT man
 ‘the man who harnessed the reindeer’
- (5) [xasava-' pod'er-mi-"] ti-"
 man-GEN harness-PSTPRT-PL reindeer-PL
 ‘the reindeer which the man harnessed’
- (6) [luc'eku-m-d mə-ma] ja-han-d mas'ibt'e-d
 spoon-ACC-2SG take-PSTPRT place-ALL-2SG put-IPR.2SG.SGO
 ‘Put the spoon in the place from which you took it.’

Now, the Uralic languages of Europe have not completely abandoned nonfinite subordination, including to express relative clauses, but nonfinite equivalents of finite relative clauses (and several other kinds of subordinate clauses) are more usual in literary or archaic (including sometimes folkloric) language. Finnish examples are given in (7)–(9).

- (7) [pommi-n löytä-nyt] koira
 bomb-ACC find-PSTPRT dog
 ‘the dog which found a bomb’
- (8) [kaupa-sta oste-ttu] kirja
 shop-ELA buy-PSTPRT.PAS book
 ‘the book (which was) bought in a shop’
- (9) [Peka-n osta-ma] auto
 Pekka-GEN buy-3INF car
 ‘the car (which was) bought by Pekka/which Pekka bought’

But although these examples illustrate nonfinite relative clauses parallel to those found in, for instance, Nenets, there are also substantial differences. First, the Finnish nonfinite construction is overall restricted to applying only to the relativizing of subjects and direct objects. Such a restriction makes no sense in terms of the grammars of Uralic languages that have undergone less Indo-European influence, but does make sense when viewed from the perspective of Indo-European: Indo-European languages also typically have alternative, less preferred participial strategies in addition to finite relative clauses, but these constructions are heavily constrained, typically only allowing relativization of subjects. Moreover, whereas Nenets uses the same nonfinite form no matter what position is relativized, Finnish has distinct forms for relativizing subjects or agents (as in (7)), direct objects or patients of constructions with an unexpressed agent (as in (8)), and direct objects of constructions with an expressed agent (as in (9)). This mirrors at least in part the use of active and passive participles in Indo-European languages, the former allowing one to relativize on agents, the latter allowing one to relativize on direct objects.

What I hope to have shown by these examples is that the influence of Indo-European syntax on Uralic languages of Europe is actually even more pervasive than is usually acknowledged: not only does it involve the adoption of finite subordination strategies, but at least in the case of relative clauses it even involves the imposition of Indo-European-like constraints on nonfinite relative clauses.²

When one turns to morphology, starting with inflectional morphology, one finds that Indo-European has had little influence on actual morphological forms and inventories in Uralic languages. An obvious example to illustrate this is case in nouns. Even conservative Indo-European languages like the Baltic and Slavic languages typically stick to around six cases (sometimes plus a vocative), and several Indo-European languages have gone some way towards reducing this number, as with the four-case system of German or the two-case system (including the genitive) of Swedish. Not only have the Uralic languages failed to reduce the six or so cases they inherited from Proto-Uralic, they have actually gone in the opposite direction by creating new cases, to give the 14 or so cases usually attributed to Finnish, the at least 18 or so usually attributed to Hungarian; in some Balto-Finnic languages, such as Estonian but not standard Finnish, a new comitative case has developed recently from the grammaticalization of a postposition.

But again, if one considers morphology more broadly, a somewhat more nuanced picture emerges. Let us consider the relation between inchoative and causative members of verb pairs such as English intransitive *open* (as in *the door opened*) and transitive *open* (as in *the boy opened the door*). Haspelmath (1993) suggests a methodology for investigating this topic cross-linguistically by first

² Balthasar Bickel informs me that one finds the opposite development in contact between Indo-European and Tibeto-Burman languages in the Himalayas. Nepali has taken the inherited restricted participial relative clause as found in other Indo-European languages and generalized it to allow relativization on virtually all positions, thus paralleling the syntax of neighboring Tibeto-Burman languages.

establishing a small number of types of relations that can obtain between inchoative and causative members of such a pair, and then assigning a profile to each language on the basis of the number of verb pairs from a fixed list of 31 basic verbal concepts that are expressed by each of these types. Of the five types identified by Haspelmath, three will be of relevance here. Table 1 illustrates them using Hungarian material. In an anticausative pair, the inchoative is derived (in the clearest cases, by affixation) from the causative. In a causative pair, the derivation is the inverse. In an equipollent pair, both inchoative and causative members of the pair are marked.

Table 1: Types of relations between inchoative and causative members of verb pairs

	Inchoative	Causative
Anticausative (A)	<i>befejeződik</i> ‘finish (vi)’	<i>befejez</i> ‘finish (vt)’
Causative (C)	<i>elég</i> ‘burn (vi)’	<i>elég-et</i> ‘burn (vt)’
Equipollent (E)	<i>jav-ul</i> ‘improve (vi)’	<i>jav-ít</i> ‘improve (vt)’

Table 2 gives the number of verbs from the 31-verb list that show each of these three types in a number of Indo-European and Uralic languages of Europe.³

Table 2: Transitivity profiles of selected European languages

	A	C	E
Finnish	4.5	14	6.5
Udmurt ⁴	10.5	12.5	4.5
Hungarian	7	9	12
Russian	23	0	5
Lithuanian	17.5	6	6
German	15.5	1	4
Swedish	19	4	3

Nichols (1993 and elsewhere) has noted that the basic pattern of a language, with predominance of causatives or anticausatives, tends to be quite stable

³ For the data, see Haspelmath (1993) and Comrie (2005). The decimals reflect verb concepts for which two verb pairs are readily available, each being then assigned half a point. The figures given here differ slightly from those given by Haspelmath for German, substantially for those given for Finnish (Haspelmath has A 12, C 13.5, E 0.5); for discussion, see Comrie (2005), although the not always transparent segmentability of Finnish verb derivational morphology makes it hard to resolve the issue.

⁴ Udmurt, also known as Votyak, is a Uralic language spoken by about half a million people in Udmurtia, a constituent republic of the Russian Federation, located between the Volga River and the Ural mountains.

over time;⁵ moreover, there is a cross-linguistic tendency for far more languages to prefer causatives than to prefer anticausatives. Indo-European languages, perhaps especially Indo-European languages of Europe, are somewhat exceptional in giving clear preference to deriving intransitives from transitives (typically by means of at least erstwhile reflexive pronouns, although other techniques, such as the middle voice in Modern Greek, are sometimes used). This is clear from the entries for Russian, Lithuanian, German, and Swedish in table 2. By contrast, the Uralic languages form a substantial proportion of such pairs using causative derivation: in each language, even accepting Haspelmath's analysis of the Finnish data (see footnote 3), there are more causative than anticausative pairs. In order to work out sufficient details of the historical development, it would be necessary also to examine Uralic languages of Siberia, to see whether they have proportions similar to those of the Uralic languages of Europe or a higher proportion of causatives. If the latter, this would be clear evidence for some shift of the Proto-Uralic pattern in the direction of more anticausatives, accommodating, but only partially, to the Indo-European pattern. The Hungarian profile is perhaps particularly interesting here, since Hungarian stands out even from the other Uralic languages by having a high number of equipollent pairs. This might be viewed as a compromise between the inherited Uralic pattern (with predominance of causatives) and the pattern of neighboring Indo-European languages (with predominance of anticausatives): in a sense, an equipollent pair has both a causative and an anticausative suffix.

2. Contact within the lexicon: Haruai

The second test case that I want to examine concerns contact involving Haruai, a Papuan (non-Austronesian) language of Papua New Guinea on which I did fieldwork in the mid-1980s. I have shown elsewhere (e.g. Comrie 2000) that Haruai is closely related to two languages spoken to the south, namely Hagahai and Pinai, on the basis of virtually identical systems of personal pronouns and of verb morphology — on these criteria, the languages are impressionistically no more different from one another than are Italian and Spanish; by these same criteria, there is no discernable genealogical relation between Haruai and its neighbor to the east, Kobon. When one turns to basic vocabulary, however, Haruai turns out to have approximately as many words shared with Kobon and not with Hagahai as it has shared with Hagahai and not with Kobon. (The actual statistics using one word list are 35% shared between Haruai and Kobon, 37% shared between Haruai and Hagahai.) I suggested further that the lexical statistics reflect substantial borrowing from Kobon into Haruai.⁶ I argued further that an important factor in this heavy borrowing is word taboo.

⁵ In the sense that a language is unlikely rapidly to adopt wholesale anticausative, causative, or equipollent derivation. Of course, a language can always lose morphology, as English has done, with the result that English has overwhelmingly a labile relation between inchoatives and causatives, i.e. the same form for both, as in the English translations in Table 1.

⁶ The direction of borrowing can usually be established unequivocally, by comparing other languages related to Kobon, in particular Kalam, the next language along to the east.

Word taboo as manifested in Haruai society means not saying the names of one's in-laws or of one's cross-cousins (i.e. father's sister's or mother's brother's children). And since people's names are typically common nouns (and occasionally even other parts of speech), this means that those common nouns are also tabooed. In Comrie (2000) I argue that this has led in some cases to the adoption of a Kobon loan to the exclusion of whatever native term must have preceded, as in the case of *ram* 'house' and *rmj* 'ear', and to the development of synonymous doublets to facilitate lexical replacement when required by word taboo. For instance, the original Haruai words *wõñõ* 'dog' and *nayõ* 'sun' exist alongside counterparts borrowed from Kobon, *kayn* and *sdõ*, respectively. The existence of such synonym pairs, not otherwise differentiated semantically or stylistically, is a strong argument in favor of the hypothesis that Haruai has undergone considerable borrowing of basic vocabulary from Kobon. This is important given claims in the literature that borrowing can reliably be detected in terms of differences between basic vocabulary (less likely to be affected) and non-basic vocabulary (more likely to be affected).

But we can take the argument a stage further. One thing that struck me in working on Haruai was the number of basic body parts that appear at least etymologically to be compounds, and are often even transparent synchronically. One might expect the word for 'mouth' to be monomorphemic, but in Haruai it is *aj möl*, where *möl* means 'hole'. The word *aj* does not simply mean 'mouth', though: not only is it never found in this form in isolation, but it participates in compounds connected not only with the mouth (such as *aj mag* 'tooth') but also with the nose, as in *höŋ aj*; incidentally, *höŋ* does participate in other compounds to do with the nose, as in *höŋ möl* 'nostril'. The word for 'eye' is *mömog*, and although this is probably not synchronically analyzable as a compound, since *mö* does not occur even in other compounds meaning 'eye', there is good evidence that it is one etymologically. The word *mag* means 'lump' and is frequent in compounds referring to small objects. Although *mö* does not otherwise occur meaning eye, a slightly different form *möp* does occur in compounds, e.g. *möp röbö* 'tear' (where *röbö* is 'water'). It thus seems that an original word *möp* remains in several compounds, but that the word for 'eye' has been reanalyzed as monomorphemic. Something similar seems to have happened with the two words for 'hand, arm', *yŋ* and *ymag*, where the latter is presumably the former, slightly reduced, in an erstwhile compound with *mag*. Variants for 'foot, leg' are more radically different, with no etymological relation between them: one is monomorphemic *yam*, the other the transparent *höb röb-b* 'feces tread-NMZ', i.e. 'that which treads on feces', no doubt referring to the not always particularly clean paths used by humans and pigs alike.

I would suggest that these are further manifestations of word taboo. Basic names of body parts can also be tabooed, and must therefore be replaced. Here we see, in addition to the possibility of borrowing from Kobon, another possible mechanism, namely the development of circumlocutions, either by creating new circumlocutions (like *höb röb-b* 'foot, leg'), or by slightly modifying compounds so that they give the appearance of not containing the offending lexical item, as when *mömog* 'eye' does not literally contain *möp*. All of this adds up to further

reinforcement of the hypothesis that word taboo is an important factor in lexical replacement in Haruai, and more generally to the importance that must be attached to the social situation in any study of language contact.

Given this, one might wonder why, in section 1, I paid so little attention to the social situation underlying contact between Uralic and Indo-European languages in Europe. In part, it is because we do not have at our disposal such detailed knowledge as we have in an ongoing process like lexical replacement in Haruai. In part, it is because the situation was probably quite complex and fluctuating over time. One tends to think of Indo-European languages as being in a dominant position with respect to Uralic languages, and thus of the influence of Indo-European on Uralic as reflecting borrowing rather than language shift, in the terminology introduced by Thomason and Kaufman (1988). But this need not always have been the case, and indeed we know of instances where things were not so. The Hungarian language was almost certainly introduced by a small social elite into a largely Slavic-speaking medieval Pannonia, with subsequent language shift from Slavic (and possibly other languages) to Hungarian. The linguistic evidence certainly points to much greater accommodation of the relevant Uralic languages to Indo-European patterns rather than the other way round. The recent history of interaction between Finnish and Swedish in Finland shows even greater complexity: since the mid-nineteenth century, large numbers of Swedish-speakers have shifted to Finnish — but they are descendants of Finnish-speakers who some generations before shifted from Finnish to Swedish! It may well be that in some cases the most important factor has been the number of bilingual speakers who have ended up using similar or identical general morphosyntactic patterns in their two languages, rather than specifically undergoing borrowing or language shift.

3. Formal constraints on borrowing: Mexicano

In the preceding, I have emphasized the importance of social factors in language contact, and it is now time to return to considering the possible influence of structural factors. In much recent work on language contact, it has been claimed — I believe correctly — that in principle anything can be adopted from one language into another, provided the right social conditions are present. In other words, there is no particular linguistic phenomenon that we can identify as untransferable. Attempts to find constraints on such transfer have therefore tended to concentrate on establishing hierarchies of transferability, such that X can only be transferred if Y is also transferred, but not vice versa; and at least since Thomason and Kaufman (1988) the answers have often been different depending on whether one is examining a case of borrowing or one of language shift.

But another way of approaching the problem would be to ask if some feature, though in principle transferable from language A to language B, might in fact not be transferable because of some property of language B — although it could be transferred to language C which lacks this property. A particular case study of this kind is developed by Field (2002) in his study of Mexicano, the variety of Nahuatl currently spoken in Mexico and having undergone intense contact with Spanish. Note that given the social relation between Mexicano (or

earlier: Nahuatl) and Spanish in Mexico, the influence of Spanish on Mexicano is almost certainly one of borrowing: there are not and have not been for centuries any substantial numbers of Spanish speakers shifting to Nahuatl/Mexicano.

Field examines the relation between borrowability and morphological typology, using the traditional division into isolating, agglutinating, and fusional languages. His hypothesis is that an isolating language will not be able to borrow agglutinating or fusional morphology, and that moreover an agglutinating language will not be able to borrow fusional morphology, while a fusional language will in principle be able to borrow any of these; in other words, there is a hierarchy: isolating > agglutinating > fusional. Of the languages involved in the contact situation investigated, Spanish is a fusional language, although particular morphemes may be agglutinating, whereas Mexicano/Nahuatl is agglutinating. The prediction would thus be that Mexicano can borrow Spanish agglutinating morphology, but not Spanish fusional morphology. And this prediction is borne out: Mexicano has borrowed the Spanish plural affix *-s*, a piece of agglutinating morphology, but has borrowed none of the fusional morphology of Spanish.

In evaluating this claim, it is important to be clear exactly what is borrowed in particular language contact situations. For instance, in the case of some Balto-Finnic languages, it is sometimes claimed that the traditional agglutinating morphology of Uralic languages is moving in the direction of fusional morphology, under the influence of neighboring Indo-European languages with their largely fusional morphology. A comparison of some examples from Finnish, in this respect a more conservative language, and Estonian, a more innovating language, will illustrate the phenomenon involved. In Finnish, as in reconstructed Proto-Uralic, the genitive is formed by adding a suffix *-n*, e.g. *talo* 'house', genitive *talo-n*, *luola* 'cave', genitive *luola-n*. By a process of consonant gradation common to the Balto-Finnic languages, certain consonants undergo alternation depending on whether they introduce an open syllable or a closed syllable. Since the genitive suffix closes its syllable, some consonants will be different as between nominative and genitive, e.g. *kukka* 'flower', genitive *kuka-n* (with geminate *kk* reduced to single *k*), *jalka* 'foot', genitive *jala-n* (with complete loss of the *k*). Although consonant gradation is to a considerable extent morphologized in Finnish, it is still possible to identify a basically agglutinating structure here, with a genitive suffix *-n* and a stem, albeit one undergoing some morphophonemic variation. For the ensuing comparison with Estonian, it will be worth also including the Finnish partitive, with the suffix *-a*, i.e. *talo-a*, *luola-a*, *kukka-a*, *jalka-a*.

Estonian has undergone a number of phonological changes that disrupt the transparency of this system. In particular, original final consonants and short vowels (more accurately: final vowel moras) are lost. Let us examine the effects of this on case forms of the Estonian word for 'foot'. The nominative is *jalg*, lacking the final vowel of its Finnish counterpart.⁷ The genitive is *jala*, lacking the final nasal of the Finnish, but still showing the effects of consonant gradation. The partitive is *jalga*, with loss of the final vowel mora relative to its Finnish counterpart. This means in particular that genitive and partitive are differentiated solely

⁷Note that in Estonian spelling, *g* corresponds to Finnish *k*, while *k* corresponds to Finnish *kk*.

by means of different forms of the stem, i.e. fusional morphology. The same effects can be seen in *välk* ‘lightning’, genitive *välgu*, partitive *välku*, with no trace of the segmental partitive suffix seen in Finnish. In relating genitive and nominative to one another, there are two possible analyses, neither of which is ideally agglutinating. Either one assumes that the final vowel found in the genitive is part of the stem, in which case the nominative is formed by truncation; or one assumes that the final vowel is not part of the stem, in which case one has to recognize declension classes depending on which vowel is added to form the genitive (and other cases, such as the partitive): on this latter analysis, *jalg* would belong to the *a*-declension, while *välk* would belong to the *u*-declension.

Let us suppose that contact with Indo-European languages was at least partially responsible for the development of fusional morphology in Estonian. Would this constitute a counterexample to Field’s hypothesis on the non-borrowability of fusional morphology by an agglutinating language? Following Field, I think that the answer must be negative. Estonian has not borrowed a particular piece of fusional morphology from one of its Indo-European neighbors, such as the Latvian first declension genitive singular suffix *-a* (cf. genitive plural *-u*). Rather, a number of sound changes, plus some morphological analogy, have conspired to give Estonian a morphological pattern that involves a fair amount of fusion. The pattern may well have been transferred from Indo-European, even though no individual form has been transferred.

It is quite generally important to keep in mind the distinction between the transfer of a particular form into another language and the transfer of a particular pattern. For instance, in his study of contact between Basque and Romance varieties in southern France, Haase (1992: 61–81) does not detect any influence of the form of Romance on the case system of Basque, but does note that the semantics of particular Basque cases is sometimes brought into line with that of their closest Romance correspondences, such as the use of the comitative to indicate not only accompaniment but also instrument. One finds similar examples in vocabulary. The Tok Pisin word *brata* clearly derives from English *brother*. But the fact that in many varieties of Tok Pisin it means not ‘brother’ but rather ‘sibling of the same sex’ (i.e. the brother of a male speaker, but the sister of a female speaker) reflects the pattern of kinship terms in the relevant indigenous languages of the New Guinea area.

4. Language mixing: Michif

A particularly important role in recent discussions of language contact has been played by so-called mixed languages, of which the best documented is probably Michif, the language of the Métis ethnic group in North Dakota (USA) and Saskatchewan and Manitoba (Canada) (Bakker 1997). As described in more detail by Bakker, Michif has a verb and clause structure that is essentially Algonquian, more specifically Cree in nature, but a noun phrase structure that is essentially French in nature. Given that the grammar is split in this way, the language can be assigned unequivocally neither to the Algonquian family nor to the Romance (Italic) branch of the Indo-European family, and must be regarded historically as

the intertwining of Cree and French components. I believe that this characterization is basically correct, and thus establishes a case where two languages have influenced one another in a way that is characterized neither as borrowing nor as language shift; but before accepting this conclusion, it is important to consider some of the objections that have been raised against it.

What seems to be clear and uncontroversial is that the Cree part of Michif involves productive syntax and morphology. What is controversial, however, is whether the same can be said of the French part. Obviously, if it can be shown that the French part does not involve productive syntax and morphology, then Michif would be characterizable as an Algonquian language that has undergone perhaps considerable influence from French, but without thereby ceasing to be an Algonquian language. Those who question the mixed language nature of Michif argue that the pieces of French one undoubtedly finds in Michif are frozen expressions. An analogy from English will make this clear. At least in higher stylistic varieties of English, one finds frequent Latin expressions, such as *de facto* and *post factum*. In Latin, *factum* and *facto* are different case forms, accusative and ablative respectively. Could one claim on this basis that English has a rich case system, albeit one restricted to one component of its lexicon? The answer is surely “no”, because this part of English vocabulary is completely unproductive: one cannot create new expressions of this kind exploiting the fact that in Latin different prepositions require different cases. Indeed, a further piece of evidence is the fact that speakers of English who are insufficiently familiar with Latin often make errors. I recently had occasion to correct something written by an extremely intelligent, educated, and literate colleague who had firmly believed up to that point that the correct English expression was *post facto*!

One of the major pieces of French morphology in the Michif noun phrase system is the gender system, since Michif, like French, appears at least *prima facie* to have two genders, clearly distinguished in the singular, for instance by means of different forms of the articles, possessive pronouns, and pronominal adjectives (Bakker 1997: 103–108). Can these all be treated as frozen expressions? It may be noted at the outset that Michif certainly has some examples where a French definite article has been reinterpreted as part of the stem, as in *lamur* ‘love’ (French *l’amour*), but even French itself has some examples of this kind, as in Modern French *lierre* ‘ivy’ (and thus *le lierre* ‘the ivy’) for Old French *iere* ‘ivy’, *l’iere* ‘the ivy’, the word deriving historically from Latin *hedera*.

Michif appears to have two forms of the article in the singular, masculine *li* and feminine *la*, as in *li bwa* ‘the wood’ and *la m̃zũ* ‘the house’. But could these be analyzed as monomorphemic, paralleling *lamur* above? Examination of further data shows that the answer must clearly be “no”. Michif also makes a gender distinction in the indefinite article, with masculine *ã* and feminine *en*, as in *ã spjũ* ‘a spy’ and *en fam* ‘a wife’. Given that the lexical distribution of *li* parallels that of *ã*,⁸ while the lexical distribution of *la* parallels that of *en*, we are clearly not dealing with monomorphemic sequences, but rather with agreement between the articles and the noun in gender. This conclusion is strengthened when we see that another item has a parallel gender distinction, namely the possessive

⁸ With the proviso that, as in French, the indefinite article is compatible only with count nouns.

pronouns used for a singular possessor, such as masculine *mu* or *mũ*, feminine *ma* ‘my’. Incidentally, the fact that some Michif words have a different gender from their French correspondents also suggests that such elements as the articles are not simply frozen parts of the word: if French *la chèvre* ‘the goat’ was heard and interpreted as a single item, there would be no expectation for it to change to *li šev(r)* in Michif. Likewise, loans from English are assigned gender, e.g. *la dam* ‘the dam’, although English provides no basis for a frozen article.

The situation with adjectives, which agree in gender in French, is more complex in Michif. In Michif, postnominal adjectives do not agree in gender, while prenominal adjectives do agree in gender. The adjectives that are prenominal in Michif are essentially the same as those that are habitually prenominal in French, so that we get examples like *ã gru sarpã* ‘a large snake’ versus *la grus tãt* ‘the big tent’. Michif certainly ends up with much less gender agreement of adjectives than French has, but such agreement as it has seems reasonably robust. This is an important general point: a particular kind of agreement can be quite restricted in a language, but nonetheless very robust. In English, number agreement of attributes is restricted to the demonstratives *this/these* and *that/those* (with the latter appearing as *that/them* in nonstandard usage); despite the unique nature of this agreement within the English noun phrase, it is robust not only within the standard language but also in (non-pidginized, non-creolized) dialects.

In sum, attempts to “explain away” the French component of Michif in terms of ordinary borrowing and frozen affixes are not tenable. Of course, if one insists on restricting the term “mixed language” to a language that takes exactly 50% from one source and exactly 50% from another, then there are probably no mixed languages, since it is unlikely that one would ever find exactly equal mixtures — even assuming there is a clear-cut way of calculating this! Michif appears to be more Cree than French, but nonetheless it is virtually impossible to construct a noun phrase without resorting to productive French-based morphosyntax, and this is the intuition underlying the notion of mixed language. Whence one must conclude, on the basis of the Michif evidence, that mixed languages do exist, even if they require specific social circumstances to come into being: in the case of Michif, a new ethnic group arising, identifying neither with Cree nor with French Canadians, from the intermarriage of local Cree-speaking women and French-speaking fur traders.

5. Detecting language shift: Celtic and English

Especially since the publication of Thomason and Kaufman (1988), the phenomenon of language shift has been at the forefront of attention. But especially as we go further back into history, the problem of identifying language shift can become acute. One need only think of the numerous instances of traditional claims about substrate influence (e.g. of Etruscan on Tuscan Italian) that have remained inconclusive despite generations of scholarly discussion. In this section, I wish to consider if there are ways in which we might advance the possibilities for identifying “ancient” language shift. Being able to do so would of course

immeasurably advance our ability to detect and analyze language contact situations in the more distant past.

One part of this overall effort would be to examine in greater detail clear cases of language shift that are ongoing or that have occurred recently and that can be investigated in sufficient detail to make their status as instances of language shift uncontroversial, and then look for parallel examples in the past. For instance, in Ireland over the past two centuries there has been a documented substantial shift from Irish to English, with the island shifting from being basically Irish-speaking to being basically English-speaking, even disregarding colonization by English-speakers (which was particularly strong only in the northeast). One legacy of this shift has been the inclusion of a number of constructions characteristic of Irish into the basilectal English of Ireland, or Hiberno-English, that are not possible in other varieties of English. One is an Irish construction expressing attendant circumstance that uses the coordinating conjunction *agus* ‘and’, as in (10), which is more literally ‘he stood there and his back to the wall’.

- (10) Bhí sé ina sheasamh ansin
was he in.his standing there
agus a dhroim leis an mballa.
and his back with.it the wall
‘He stood there with his back to the wall.’

This construction carries over into Hiberno-English, as in example (11), from Sean O’Casey’s *The plough and the stars*. In this example, standard English would require something like *if he were dead*.

- (11) ... you’d have as much chance o’ movin’ Fluther as a tune on a tinwhistle
would move a deaf man an’ he dead.

We may now examine putative cases of language shift to see if such examples — where a phenomenon is plausibly attributed to the substrate language and cannot plausibly be attributed to the target language of the language shift — can be identified. A nice example to start with, in part because it has traditionally been regarded as insoluble, is the linguistic Anglicization of England and southern Scotland. We know from the historical record that this area was Celtic-speaking through to the end of Roman rule in Britain in the early fifth century, and equally we know that by a few hundred years later it was solidly English-speaking. Did this involve the expulsion of the Celtic-speaking population by speakers of Old English, or was there rather substantial language shift from British Celtic to Old English? The historical record is largely silent on this question, so one must seek for more indirect evidence. One that has played a role in recent discussions is the so-called Northern Subject Rule (Klemola 2000), whereby in many northern English dialects verb agreement in the present tense follows in general the same pattern as in the standard languages, except that a third person nonpronominal plural subject takes the same verb form as a third person singular subject, in

contrast to a third person pronominal subject, giving a paradigm as illustrated partially in (12).

- (12) he runs
the boy runs
they run
the boys runs

The crucial form is the last one, which contrasts with standard English *the boys run*. It turns out that we find a very similar phenomenon in Welsh, as shown in the partial paradigm of the verb ‘to be’ in (13).⁹

- (13) y mae ef ‘he is’
y mae’r bachgen ‘the boy is’
y maent hwy ‘they are’
y mae’r bechgyn ‘the boys are’

In other words, we have close parallelism between a construction in a descendant of the putative substratum language and a construction in one set of dialects of the language suspected to have been influenced by this substratum; crucially, the construction in question finds no clear basis internally to English. Moreover, it is significant that the Northern Subject Rule is found precisely in dialects of the north of the traditionally English-speaking part of Britain, an area where historians have on independent grounds suspected that the Celtic population might have survived longer, with a distinct ethnic and linguistic identity, than further to the south.

As my final point before concluding, I would like to mention one further kind of evidence that can be indicative of language shift, this time going beyond linguistics in the direction of interdisciplinary cooperation. The example that interests me is the establishment of the Turkic language Azerbaijani in Azerbaijan, in the Caucasus. We know from the historical record that Turkic languages entered the Caucasus about a thousand years ago, so a similar question arises as in the case of the Anglicization of England: did this involve the expulsion of the earlier population, or was it rather a case of language shift to the language of a dominant elite? Here, evidence from population genetics can play a key role. Nasidze and Stoneking (2001) examine the evidence from genetics for relations among selected peoples of the Caucasus, concluding that on the basis of genetics the Azerbaijani fall well within the general range of variation found within the Caucasus and are much more distinct from Turkic-speaking populations found elsewhere, whether in Turkey or in Central Asia. This suggests that the Azerbaijani-ization of Azerbaijan was indeed primarily a case of language shift. The

⁹The structure of the Welsh examples is an initial affirmative particle followed by the appropriate form of the verb ‘to be’ followed by the subject noun phrase, consisting in the case of nonpronominal subjects of the definite article (with the form *r* after a vowel) followed by the noun.

powerful tools provided by population genetics open up new perspectives on the identification of language shift. Wherever a population A groups linguistically with population B, but in terms of genetics with population C, we have prima facie evidence for language shift. Working out the details requires intensive cooperation between the two disciplines of historical linguistics and population genetics.

6. Conclusion

In this article I have tried to examine a number of case studies of language contact to ascertain what light they throw on the effects of language contact, in particular in establishing constraints on the linguistic effects of such contact, on preferences among these linguistic effects. I have tried to emphasize the importance of considering social factors, whether this is to enable us to identify cases of borrowing in the strict sense, language shift (with an important new contribution from population genetics), mixed languages, or instances of structural accommodation in the minds of bilingual speakers; in the discussion of Haruai I emphasized the importance of social factors even in a case that is rather clearly one of borrowing. I have also tried to emphasize structural factors, ranging from the different degrees of permeability of different parts of a language to different kinds of language contact, through the difference between transferring particular forms and transferring more general patterns, to hypotheses concerning constraints on borrowability related to the structure of the borrowing language. If I have succeeded in raising as many questions as I have answered, I will consider my task successfully accomplished.

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